

Online IDentity Theft Victim support guidelines

Being a victim of Online Identity Theft (OIDT) can be a **traumatic experience** and can have **physical and/or psychological consequences** to take care of.

It is important victims don't deny the experience, talk about their feelings, explain to people their point of view about what happened, process the event to overcome it.

How?

- (1) **Encourage listening and the dialogue close to the victim** *talking to family members, partners, friends and/or people the victim trusts may help reflect on what happened.*
- (2) **Suggest and reason on the necessity of reporting the crime suffered and contacting a lawyer (public or private)** *even if this is a personal decision of the victim, it should be emphasised that reporting enables the victim to assert her/his legal rights, to ask for compensation and obtain - if necessary – protection. Moreover, reporting helps to make this crime more visible and known to Law Enforcement and society.*
- (3) **Inform and/or help in seeking for a therapist and/or psychosocial associations offer support to victims of digital crime.** *Victims, indeed, could prefer talk to someone outside their family, partners or circle of friends.*
- (4) **Pay attention to the victim general wellbeing, don't make her/him feel lonely and/or judged** *suggest to seek medical help if physical and/or emotional situation worsens.*
- (5) **Suggest and/or help to keep a textual and visual diary** where victims could be able to (a) record events and collecting screenshots, text messages, emails or anything that may be useful to support their story; (b) record moods by writing, drawing, cutting, sewing, taking photos etc.

T I P S

IF YOU ARE SUPPORTING OIDD VICTIMS

YOU CAN...

- Believe them
- Spend time with them
- Listen carefully
- Tell them you are sorry to hear about the event and that you want to help them
- Help them feel safe
- Help them with everyday tasks
- Avoid judging

REMEMBER...

- Do not be afraid to ask questions and to explore the issues
- Do not take angry outbursts personally
- Do not say things like "you're lucky, it could have been worse" or "never mind, get on with your life"
- Do not say things that imply it was their fault, for example "Why did you believe/click on that message?"
- Do not be impatient with them – people recover at different rates